

**ECONOMY UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IMPROVING
PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE THROUGH THE
CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING**

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ABSTRACT

The main task in the organization and conduct of the educational process is the development and consistent elements of actions leading to a pre-planned result. In the transition to credit education, not all scientists accepted the paradigm of credit-module education, that is the student should learn on his own and the teacher should organize and motivate. Modern pedagogy has come to the conclusion that successful results are achieved there should be no fixed time for individual characteristics of assimilation and individual speed of learning the material.

Introduction

One of the most important tasks for the educational system of every country is to develop the most effective methods of education and to introduce them into the activities of educational institutions. If we look at it from this point of view, the attitude of our country to learning foreign languages has never been as important as it is now. Because at that time there were almost no political, economic, cultural, scientific, technical and other relations and connections with foreign countries of different systems.

Today, the implementation of political, economic, scientific-technical, cultural and educational relations with foreign countries in the independent Republic of Uzbekistan requires the introduction and improvement of advanced methods of teaching foreign languages in educational institutions due to the need to train qualified personnel who know foreign languages perfectly. For this reason, in the years of independence, the interest and demand for improving the methods of teaching foreign languages, increasing its quality and efficiency is increasing.

It is recognized in world pedagogy that economic education is given great importance in world friendship. After all, the economy affects all spheres of society's life to a certain extent. Economic activity, as noted by Taylor, is not the priority of all sectors, but its importance is significant in any society.

The goal of the reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan is economic strategy and development, aimed at further improvement of tax, financial and monetary policy, as well as liberalization of foreign economic activity. It is up to the youth to fully

solve these problems. Therefore, students should study the acquired economic knowledge starting from the general secondary, secondary-special vocational education systems and perfect it in the higher education system. Because the training of highly qualified economic personnel for the independent Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the most urgent problems of today.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

It is known that those who enter economic higher educational institutions graduate from secondary school or secondary special vocational education institutions. Foreign language teaching should also be fully focused on the economics majors of undergraduate students. After all, whatever profession a student has chosen and what he is studying in economic higher educational institutions, he should start studying economic texts, words, expressions, and terms in foreign languages related to this profession. Because, first of all, future economists should be able to communicate freely about their chosen specialty, whether they work in joint ventures established in Uzbekistan, foreign companies or go to other foreign countries to continue their work. In today's practical language education, this language is called learning for special purposes and is opposed to the basic concept of language. So (in English, the first is called "Language for specific (special) purpose", and the second is called General or Basic sometimes Social Language).

Therefore, the basics of foreign language education are taught in the continuous education system in preschool education, primary and secondary school. After graduating from an academic lyceum and a vocational college, students who come to economic higher education institutions must learn the basics of a foreign language. Through the basics of language, the language used to communicate with people of various professions is taught through words and phrases used in everyday life, formal and informal conversations. A special language is a communication language used in business between people of the same profession. In fact, they are two different forms of the same language, mainly a division within the lexical layer of the language, the phonetic and grammatical layers of the language are common to the types of speech activity noted. It follows from this that if language education is done correctly, students should have learned foreign language phonetics, grammar and universal lexicon by the time they come to economic higher education institutions.

When teaching foreign languages, especially English for special purposes, these are certainly important, but the communicative method is a component of the grammar of the language, and their more or less use depends on the type of speech.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is known that a child reflects in his speech what he has seen and the names of his actions from birth to school. When learning foreign languages, in particular English, it is necessary to learn the subjects, actions, customs, geographical conditions, paralinguistic features called in a foreign language only through imagination, therefore, mastering foreign languages, in particular English, is somewhat difficult. For this, we need to teach foreign languages, especially English, to speak fluently and grammatically correctly, but in the eyes of foreigners, we appear to have made a number of shortcomings. The reason is the lack of harmony between the practical life of this people and learning their language.

Therefore, the introduction of video courses into the teaching process serves to create this harmony, at least a little. In today's market economy, the purchase of necessary technical means for audio-video courses requires a lot of money. But we should not spare them money to improve the teaching of foreign languages, including English language teaching.

Therefore, training of mature economic personnel is becoming one of the important issues in building our prosperous future, in fundamentally changing the system of higher economic education and in raising it to the level of current demand. From the first years of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been paying great attention to restoring and further improving our high spirituality, improving the national education system, and bringing it up to the standards of the world's developed countries based on the requirements of the times. In addition, the opening of the Academy of State and Society Construction and the Academy of Banking and Finance in Tashkent was particularly important. Because today, in Uzbekistan, in establishing a legal democratic state and a civil society, the authority of these economic educational institutions is very high in the banking sector and solving financial issues.

CONCLUSION

In fact, since the first days of our country's independence, work aimed at raising the importance and prestige of the economic profession has been consistently carried out, and measures aimed at improving the material living conditions of economists have been implemented.

Economic and socio-economic changes in the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years have placed new demands on higher educational institutions of economics in teaching foreign languages. Because it is not a secret to anyone that managers of various enterprises, economists, bank employees, financial engineers, auditors, accountants, tax collectors, and even ordinary workers, know one of the foreign languages. In addition, in the development of universal forms of culture, it is important to know one of the international languages in the cultural and educational development of a person. It is self-evident that the peoples of the world will continue to improve by establishing constant relations with each other in the fields of production, science and technology, culture, literature, art and education.

Teaching foreign languages, in particular English, to future economists in higher educational institutions of economics, with such lofty goals, formation of professional qualifications and skills of students in the field of economic education includes a number of economic directions, at the same time, the economy of countries that communicate in English, they increase the need to know English language based on the study of politics, production products and resources and other material wealth.

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